

Neutrosophic Closed Set and Neutrosophic Continuous Functions

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Abstract

In this paper, we introduce and study the concept of "neutrosophic closed set" and "neutrosophic continuous function". Possible application to GIS topology rules are touched upon.

Keywords: Neutrosophic Closed Set, Neutrosophic Set; Neutrosophic Topology; Neutrosophic Continuous Function.

1 INTRODUCTION

The idea of "neutrosophic set" was first given by Smarandache [11, 12]. Neutrosophic operations have been investigated by Salama at el. [1-10]. Neutrosophy has laid the foundation for a whole family of new mathematical theories, generalizing both their crisp and fuzzy counterparts [9, 13]. Here we shall present the neutrosophic crisp version of these concepts. In this paper, we introduce and study the concept of "neutrosophic closed set" and "neutrosophic continuous function".

2 TERMINOLOGIES

We recollect some relevant basic preliminaries, and in particular the work of Smarandache in [11, 12], and Salama at el. [1-10].

2.1 Definition [5]

A neutrosophic topology (NT for short) on a non empty set X is a family τ of neutrosophic subsets in X satisfying the following axioms

$$(NT_1) O_N, 1_N \in \tau,$$

$$(NT_2) G_1 \cap G_2 \in \tau \text{ for any } G_1, G_2 \in \tau,$$

$$(NT_3) \bigcup G_i \in \tau \quad \forall \{G_i : i \in J\} \subseteq \tau$$

In this case the pair (X, τ) is called a neutrosophic topological space (NTS for short) and any neutrosophic set in τ is known as neutrosophic open set (NOS for short) in X . The elements of τ are called open neutrosophic sets, A neutrosophic set F is closed if and only if its complement $C(F)$ is neutrosophic open.

2.1 Definition [5]

The complement of $C(A)$ for short) of A is called a neutrosophic closed set (NCS for short) in X . NOSA NCS X .

3 Neutrosophic Closed Set .

3.1 Definition

Let (X, τ) be a neutrosophic topological space. A neutrosophic set A in (X, τ) is said to be neutrosophic closed (in shortly N-closed).

If $Ncl(A) \subseteq G$ whenever $A \subseteq G$ and G is neutrosophic open; the complement of neutrosophic closed set is Neutrosophic open.

3.1 Proposition

If A and B are neutrosophic closed sets then $A \cup B$ is Neutrosophic closed set.

3.1 Remark

The intersection of two neutrosophic closed (N-closed for short) sets need not be neutrosophic closed set.

3.1 Example

Let $X = \{a, b, c\}$ and

$$A = \langle (0.5, 0.5, 0.5), (0.4, 0.5, 0.5), (0.4, 0.5, 0.5) \rangle$$

$$B = \langle (0.3, 0.4, 0.4), (0.7, 0.5, 0.5), (0.3, 0.4, 0.4) \rangle$$

Then $T = \{0_N, 1_N, A, B\}$ is a neutrosophic topology on X . Define the two neutrosophic sets A_1 and A_2 as follows,

$$A_1 = \langle (0.5, 0.5, 0.5), (0.6, 0.5, 0.5), (0.6, 0.5, 0.5) \rangle$$

$$A_2 = \langle (0.7, 0.6, 0.6), (0.3, 0.5, 0.5), (0.7, 0.6, 0.6) \rangle$$

A_1 and A_2 are neutrosophic closed set but $A_1 \cap A_2$ is not a neutrosophic closed set.

3.2 Proposition

Let (X, τ) be a neutrosophic topological space. If B is neutrosophic closed set and $B \subseteq A \subseteq \text{Ncl}(B)$, then A is N -closed.

3.4 Proposition

In a neutrosophic topological space (X, T) , $T = \mathfrak{T}$ (the family of all neutrosophic closed sets) iff every neutrosophic subset of (X, T) is a neutrosophic closed set.

Proof.

suppose that every neutrosophic set A of (X, T) is N -closed. Let $A \in T$, since $A \subseteq A$ and A is N -closed, $\text{Ncl}(A) \subseteq A$. But $A \subseteq \text{Ncl}(A)$. Hence, $\text{Ncl}(A) = A$. thus, $A \in \mathfrak{T}$. Therefore, $T \subseteq \mathfrak{T}$. If $B \in \mathfrak{T}$ then $1-B \in T \subseteq \mathfrak{T}$. and hence $B \in T$, That is, $\mathfrak{T} \subseteq T$. Therefore $T = \mathfrak{T}$ conversely, suppose that A be a neutrosophic set in (X, T) . Let B be a neutrosophic open set in (X, T) . such that $A \subseteq B$. By hypothesis, B is neutrosophic N -closed. By definition of neutrosophic closure, $\text{Ncl}(A) \subseteq B$. Therefore A is N -closed.

3.5 Proposition

Let (X, T) be a neutrosophic topological space. A neutrosophic set A is neutrosophic open iff $B \subseteq \text{Nint}(A)$, whenever B is neutrosophic closed and $B \subseteq A$.

Proof

Let A a neutrosophic open set and B be a N -closed, such that $B \subseteq A$. Now, $B \subseteq A \Rightarrow 1-A \Rightarrow 1-B$ and $1-A$ is a neutrosophic closed set $\Rightarrow \text{Ncl}(1-A) \subseteq 1-B$. That is, $B = 1-(1-B) \subseteq 1-\text{Ncl}(1-A)$. But $1-\text{Ncl}(1-A) = \text{Nint}(A)$. Thus, $B \subseteq \text{Nint}(A)$. Conversely, suppose that A be a neutrosophic set, such that $B \subseteq \text{Nint}(A)$ whenever B is neutrosophic closed and $B \subseteq A$. Let $1-A \subseteq B \Rightarrow 1-B \subseteq A$. Hence by assumption $1-B \subseteq \text{Nint}(A)$. that is, $1-\text{Nint}(A) \subseteq B$. But $1-\text{Nint}(A) = \text{Ncl}(1-A)$. Hence $\text{Ncl}(1-A) \subseteq B$. That is $1-A$ is neutrosophic closed set. Therefore, A is neutrosophic open set

3.6 Proposition

If $\text{Nint}(A) \subseteq B \subseteq A$ and if A is neutrosophic open set then B is also neutrosophic open set.

4 Neutrosophic Continuous Functions

4.1 Definition

i) If $B = \langle \mu_B, \sigma_B, \nu_B \rangle$ is a NS in Y , then the preimage of B under f , denoted by $f^{-1}(B)$, is a NS in X defined by $f^{-1}(B) = \langle f^{-1}(\mu_B), f^{-1}(\sigma_B), f^{-1}(\nu_B) \rangle$.

ii) If $A = \langle \mu_A, \sigma_A, \nu_A \rangle$ is a NS in X , then the image of A under f , denoted by $f(A)$, is the a NS in Y defined by $f(A) = \langle f(\mu_A), f(\sigma_A), f(\nu_A)^c \rangle$.

Here we introduce the properties of images and preimages some of which we shall frequently use in the following sections .

4.1 Corollary

Let $A, \{A_i : i \in J\}$, be NSs in X , and $B, \{B_j : j \in K\}$ NS in Y , and $f : X \rightarrow Y$ a function. Then

$$(a) A_1 \subseteq A_2 \Leftrightarrow f(A_1) \subseteq f(A_2),$$

$$B_1 \subseteq B_2 \Leftrightarrow f^{-1}(B_1) \subseteq f^{-1}(B_2),$$

(b) $A \subseteq f^{-1}(f(A))$ and if f is injective, then

$$A = f^{-1}(f(A)) .$$

(c) $f^{-1}(f(B)) \subseteq B$ and if f is surjective, then

$$f^{-1}(f(B)) = B .$$

$$(d) f^{-1}(\cup B_i) = \cup f^{-1}(B_i), f^{-1}(\cap B_i) = \cap f^{-1}(B_i),$$

(e) $f(\cup A_i) = \cup f(A_i); f(\cap A_i) \subseteq \cap f(A_i)$; and if f is injective, then $f(\cap A_i) = \cap f(A_i)$;

$$(f) f^{-1}(1_N) = 1_N, f^{-1}(0_N) = 0_N .$$

(g) $f(0_N) = 0_N, f(1_N) = 1_N$ if f is surjective.

Proof

Obvious.

4.2 Definition

Let (X, Γ_1) and (Y, Γ_2) be two NTSs, and let $f : X \rightarrow Y$ be a function. Then f is said to be continuous iff the preimage of each NCS in Γ_2 is a NS in Γ_1 .

4.3 Definition

Let (X, Γ_1) and (Y, Γ_2) be two NTSs and let $f : X \rightarrow Y$ be a function. Then f is said to be open iff the image of each NS in Γ_1 is a NS in Γ_2 .

4.1 Example

Let (X, Γ_o) and (Y, ψ_o) be two NTSs

(a) If $f : X \rightarrow Y$ is continuous in the usual sense, then in this case, f is continuous in the sense of Definition 5.1 too. Here we consider the NTs on X and Y , respectively, as follows : $\Gamma_1 = \langle \mu_G, 0, \mu_G^c \rangle : G \in \Gamma_o$ and

$$\Gamma_2 = \left\{ \langle \mu_H, 0, \mu_H^c \rangle : H \in \mathcal{P}_o \right\},$$

In this case we have, for each $\langle \mu_H, 0, \mu_H^c \rangle \in \Gamma_2$,

$$f^{-1} \left\langle \mu_H, 0, \mu_H^c \right\rangle = \left\langle f^{-1}(\mu_H), f^{-1}(0), f^{-1}(\mu_H^c) \right\rangle = \left\langle f^{-1}(\mu_H), f(0), (f(\mu))^c \right\rangle \in \Gamma_1.$$

(b) If $f : X \rightarrow Y$ is neutrosophic open in the usual sense, then in this case, f is neutrosophic open in the sense of Definition 3.2.

Now we obtain some characterizations of neutrosophic continuity:

4.1 Proposition

Let $f : (X, \Gamma_1) \rightarrow (Y, \Gamma_2)$.

f is neutrosophic continuous iff the preimage of each NS (neutrosophic closed set) in Γ_2 is a NS in Γ_1 .

4.2 Proposition

The following are equivalent to each other:

- (a) $f : (X, \Gamma_1) \rightarrow (Y, \Gamma_2)$ is neutrosophic continuous.
- (b) $f^{-1}(NInt(B)) \subseteq NInt(f^{-1}(B))$ for each CNS B in Y .
- (c) $NCl(f^{-1}(B)) \subseteq f^{-1}(NCl(B))$ for each NCB in Y .

4.2 Example

Let (Y, Γ_2) be a NTS and $f : X \rightarrow Y$ be a function. In this case $\Gamma_1 = \{f^{-1}(H) : H \in \Gamma_2\}$ is a NT on X . Indeed, it is the coarsest NT on X which makes the function $f : X \rightarrow Y$ continuous. One may call it the initial neutrosophic crisp topology with respect to f .

4.4 Definition

Let (X, T) and (Y, S) be two neutrosophic topological space, then

- (a) A map $f : (X, T) \rightarrow (Y, S)$ is called N-continuous (in short N-continuous) if the inverse image of every closed set in (Y, S) is Neutrosophic closed in (X, T) .
- (b) A map $f : (X, T) \rightarrow (Y, S)$ is called neutrosophic-gc irresolute if the inverse image of every Neutrosophic closed set in (Y, S) is Neutrosophic closed in (X, T) . Equivalently if the inverse image of every Neutrosophic open set in (Y, S) is Neutrosophic open in (X, T) .
- (c) A map $f : (X, T) \rightarrow (Y, S)$ is said to be strongly neutrosophic continuous if $f^{-1}(A)$ is both neutrosophic open and neutrosophic closed in (X, T) for each neutrosophic set A in (Y, S) .
- (d) A map $f : (X, T) \rightarrow (Y, S)$ is said to be perfectly neutrosophic continuous if $f^{-1}(A)$ is both neutrosophic open and neutrosophic closed in (X, T) for each neutrosophic open set A in (Y, S) .
- (e) A map $f : (X, T) \rightarrow (Y, S)$ is said to be strongly N-continuous if the inverse image of every Neutrosophic open set in (Y, S) is neutrosophic open in (X, T) .

(F) A map $f : (X, T) \rightarrow (Y, S)$ is said to be perfectly N-continuous if the inverse image of every Neutrosophic open set in (Y, S) is both neutrosophic open and neutrosophic closed in (X, T) .

4.3 Proposition

Let (X, T) and (Y, S) be any two neutrosophic topological spaces. Let $f : (X, T) \rightarrow (Y, S)$ be generalized neutrosophic continuous. Then for every neutrosophic set A in X , $f(Ncl(A)) \subseteq Ncl(f(A))$.

4.4 Proposition

Let (X, T) and (Y, S) be any two neutrosophic topological spaces. Let $f : (X, T) \rightarrow (Y, S)$ be generalized neutrosophic continuous. Then for every neutrosophic set A in Y , $Ncl(f^{-1}(A)) \subseteq f^{-1}(Ncl(A))$.

4.5 Proposition

Let (X, T) and (Y, S) be any two neutrosophic topological spaces. If A is a Neutrosophic closed set in (X, T) and if $f : (X, T) \rightarrow (Y, S)$ is neutrosophic continuous and neutrosophic-closed then $f(A)$ is Neutrosophic closed in (Y, S) .

Proof.

Let G be a neutrosophic-open in (Y, S) . If $f(A) \subseteq G$, then $A \subseteq f^{-1}(G)$ in (X, T) . Since A is neutrosophic closed and $f^{-1}(G)$ is neutrosophic open in (X, T) , $Ncl(A) \subseteq f^{-1}(G)$, (i.e) $f(Ncl(A)) \subseteq G$. Now by assumption, $f(Ncl(A))$ is neutrosophic closed and $Ncl(f(A)) \subseteq Ncl(f(Ncl(A))) = f(Ncl(A)) \subseteq G$. Hence, $f(A)$ is N-closed.

4.5 Proposition

Let (X, T) and (Y, S) be any two neutrosophic topological spaces, If $f : (X, T) \rightarrow (Y, S)$ is neutrosophic continuous then it is N-continuous.

The converse of proposition 4.5 need not be true. See Example 4.3.

4.3 Example

Let $X = \{a, b, c\}$ and $Y = \{a, b, c\}$. Define neutrosophic sets A and B as follows $A = \langle (0.4, 0.4, 0.5), (0.2, 0.4, 0.3), (0.4, 0.4, 0.5) \rangle$

$$B = \langle (0.4, 0.5, 0.6), (0.3, 0.2, 0.3), (0.4, 0.5, 0.6) \rangle$$

Then the family $T = \{0_N, 1_N, A\}$ is a neutrosophic topology on X and $S = \{0_N, 1_N, B\}$ is a neutrosophic topology on Y . Thus (X, T) and (Y, S) are neutrosophic topological spaces. Define $f : (X, T) \rightarrow (Y, S)$ as $f(a) = b, f(b) = a, f(c) = c$. Clearly f is N-continuous. Now f is not neutrosophic continuous, since $f^{-1}(B) \notin T$ for $B \in S$.

4.4 Example

Let $X = \{a, b, c\}$. Define the neutrosophic sets A and B as follows.

$$A = \langle (0.4, 0.5, 0.4), (0.5, 0.5, 0.5), (0.4, 0.5, 0.4) \rangle$$

$B = \langle (0.7,0.6,0.5), (0.3,0.4,0.5), (0.3,0.4,0.5) \rangle$
and $C = \langle (0.5,0.5,0.5), (0.4,0.5,0.5), (0.5,0.5,0.5) \rangle$

$T = \{0_N, 1_N, A, B\}$

and $S = \{0_N, 1_N, C\}$ are neutrosophic topologies on X . Thus (X, T) and (X, S) are neutrosophic topological spaces. Define $f: (X, T) \rightarrow (X, S)$ as follows $f(a) = b, f(b) = b, f(c) = c$. Clearly f is N -continuous. Since

$D = \langle (0.6,0.6,0.7), (0.4,0.4,0.3), (0.6,0.6,0.7) \rangle$

is neutrosophic open in (X, S) , $f^{-1}(D)$ is not neutrosophic open in (X, T) .

4.6 Proposition

Let (X, T) and (Y, S) be any two neutrosophic topological space. If $f: (X, T) \rightarrow (Y, S)$ is strongly N -continuous then f is neutrosophic continuous.

The converse of Proposition 3.19 is not true. See Example 3.3

4.5 Example

Let $X = \{a, b, c\}$. Define the neutrosophic sets A and B as follows.

$A = \langle (0.9,0.9,0.9), (0.1,0.1,0.1), (0.9,0.9,0.9) \rangle$

$B = \langle (0.9,0.9,0.9), (0.1,0.1,0.1), (0.9,0.1,0.8) \rangle$

and $C = \langle (0.9,0.9,0.9), (0.1,0,0.1), (0.9,0.9,0.9) \rangle$

$T = \{0_N, 1_N, A, B\}$ and $S = \{0_N, 1_N, C\}$ are neutrosophic topologies on X . Thus (X, T) and (X, S) are neutrosophic topological spaces. Also define $f: (X, T) \rightarrow (X, S)$ as follows $f(a) = a, f(b) = c, f(c) = b$. Clearly f is neutrosophic continuous. But f is not strongly N -continuous. Since

$D = \langle (0.9,0.9,0.99), (0.05,0,0.01), (0.9,0.9,0.99) \rangle$

Is an Neutrosophic open set in (X, S) , $f^{-1}(D)$ is not neutrosophic open in (X, T) .

4.7 Proposition

Let (X, T) and (Y, S) be any two neutrosophic topological spaces. If $f: (X, T) \rightarrow (Y, S)$ is perfectly N -continuous then f is strongly N -continuous.

The converse of Proposition 4.7 is not true. See Example 4.6

4.6 Example

Let $X = \{a, b, c\}$. Define the neutrosophic sets A and B as follows.

$A = \langle (0.9,0.9,0.9), (0.1,0.1,0.1), (0.9,0.9,0.9) \rangle$

$B = \langle (0.99,0.99,0.99), (0.01,0,0), (0.99,0.99,0.99) \rangle$

And $C = \langle (0.9,0.9,0.9), (0.1,0.1,0.05), (0.9,0.9,0.9) \rangle$

$T = \{0_N, 1_N, A, B\}$ and $S = \{0_N, 1_N, C\}$ are neutrosophic topologies space on X . Thus (X, T) and (X, S) are neutrosophic topological spaces. Also define $f: (X, T) \rightarrow (X, S)$ as follows $f(a) = a, f(b) = f(c) = b$. Clearly f is strongly N -continuous. But f is not perfectly N continuous. Since $D = \langle (0.9,0.9,0.9), (0.1,0.1,0.1), (0.9,0.9,0.9) \rangle$

Is an Neutrosophic open set in (X, S) , $f^{-1}(D)$ is neutrosophic open and not neutrosophic closed in (X, T) .

4.8 Proposition

Let (X, T) and (Y, S) be any neutrosophic topological spaces. If $f: (X, T) \rightarrow (Y, S)$ is strongly neutrosophic continuous then f is strongly N -continuous.

The converse of proposition 3.23 is not true. See Example 4.7

4.7 Example

Let $X = \{a, b, c\}$ and Define the neutrosophic sets A and B as follows.

$A = \langle (0.9,0.9,0.9), (0.1,0.1,0.1), (0.9,0.9,0.9) \rangle$

$B = \langle (0.99,0.99,0.99), (0.01,0,0), (0.99,0.99,0.99) \rangle$

and $C = \langle (0.9,0.9,0.9), (0.1,0.1,0.05), (0.9,0.9,0.9) \rangle$

$T = \{0_N, 1_N, A, B\}$ and $S = \{0_N, 1_N, C\}$ are neutrosophic topologies on X . Thus (X, T) and (X, S) are neutrosophic topological spaces. Also define $f: (X, T) \rightarrow (X, S)$ as follows: $f(a) = a, f(b) = f(c) = b$. Clearly f is strongly N -continuous. But f is not strongly neutrosophic continuous. Since

$D = \langle (0.9,0.9,0.9), (0.1,0.1,0.1), (0.9,0.9,0.9) \rangle$

be a neutrosophic set in (X, S) , $f^{-1}(D)$ is neutrosophic open and not neutrosophic closed in (X, T) .

4.9 Proposition

Let $(X, T), (Y, S)$ and (Z, R) be any three neutrosophic topological spaces. Suppose $f: (X, T) \rightarrow (Y, S)$, $g: (Y, S) \rightarrow (Z, R)$ be maps. Assume f is neutrosophic gc -irresolute and g is N -continuous then $g \circ f$ is N -continuous.

4.10 Proposition

Let $(X, T), (Y, S)$ and (Z, R) be any three neutrosophic topological spaces. Let $f: (X, T) \rightarrow (Y, S)$, $g: (Y, S) \rightarrow (Z, R)$ be map, such that f is strongly N -continuous and g is N -continuous. Then the composition $g \circ f$ is neutrosophic continuous.

4.5 Definition

A neutrosophic topological space (X, T) is said to be neutrosophic $T_{1/2}$ if every Neutrosophic closed set in (X, T) is neutrosophic closed in (X, T) .

4.11 Proposition

Let $(X, T), (Y, S)$ and (Z, R) be any neutrosophic topological spaces. Let $f: (X, T) \rightarrow (Y, S)$ and $g: (Y, S) \rightarrow (Z, R)$ be mapping and (Y, S) be neutrosophic $T_{1/2}$ if f and g are N -continuous then the composition $g \circ f$ is N -continuous.

The proposition 4.11 is not valid if (Y, S) is not neutrosophic $T_{1/2}$.

4.8 Example

Let $X = \{a, b, c\}$. Define the neutrosophic sets A, B and C as follows.

$A = \langle (0.4,0.4,0.6), (0.4,0.4,0.3) \rangle$

$B = \langle (0.4,0.5,0.6), (0.3,0.4,0.3) \rangle$

and $C = \langle (0.4,0.6,0.5), (0.5,0.3,0.4) \rangle$

Then the family $T = \{0_N, 1_N, A\}$, $S = \{0_N, 1_N, B\}$ and $R = \{0_N, 1_N, C\}$ are neutrosophic topologies on X . Thus $(X, T), (X, S)$ and (X, R) are neutrosophic topological spaces. Also define $f : (X, T) \rightarrow (X, S)$ as $f(a) = b$, $f(b) = a$, $f(c) = c$ and $g : (X, S) \rightarrow (X, R)$ as $g(a) = b$, $g(b) = c$, $g(c) = b$. Clearly f and g are N -continuous function. But $g \circ f$ is not N -continuous. For $1 - C$ is neutrosophic closed in (X, R) . $f^{-1}(g^{-1}(1-C))$ is not N closed in (X, T) . $g \circ f$ is not N -continuous.

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